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Venture Capital Investments in the Later Stage Venture Phase in OECD Countries

Increased on average by 301.44% between 2007 and 2022 in OECD countries

The OECD calculates the value of venture capital investments in the later stage phase. The data refer to the period between 2007 and 2022 and are in billions of dollars.

Venture Capital Investments in the Later Stage Venture Phase in 2022. The analysis of venture capital investments in the later stage venture phase in 2022 highlights how different economies face challenges and opportunities in financing mature and potentially profitable businesses. The United States continues to dominate the sector with significantly higher investments, totaling \$93,380.63 million. This underscores its leading position in innovation and technology, benefiting from a highly developed venture capital ecosystem and a vast network of advanced-stage companies that attract substantial investments. Israel and Canada follow at a considerable distance, investing \$8,526.35 million and \$3,303.37 million respectively. Israel, known as the "Startup Nation," shows an exceptional ability to nurture companies to the later stages of their development. Canada, with its strong focus on emerging technologies and sustainability, also reflects robust growth in venture capital, benefiting from supportive government policies and an active entrepreneurial environment. In Europe, France leads with \$2,083.98 million, followed by Germany and the United Kingdom with \$1,542.39 million and \$1,123.89 million respectively. These figures reflect strong infrastructure and policies that support innovation and financing of advanced-stage businesses. However, countries like Italy and Spain show more modest figures, which may indicate less mature venture capital markets or different economic dynamics affecting the availability of venture capital. Smaller nations such as Estonia, Lithuania, and Slovenia show more contained investments, but it is important to note that even small increases can have a significant impact on their local economies. These investments reflect a growing interest in developing startup ecosystems and may indicate an initial growth phase in their venture capital market. The 2022 data on later stage venture investments illustrate a clear discrepancy between the United States and the rest of the world, highlighting the maturity and scale of the American market. However, countries in Europe and other regions show signs of a growing environment for venture capital with varying degrees of maturity and success. Challenges for countries with lower investments include the need to further develop local ecosystems, improve regulatory and fiscal conditions, and increase the availability of domestic and international capital to support advanced stages of business development. To capitalize on these opportunities, governments

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and policymakers must consider incentives, supports, and reforms that can attract more investments in these crucial stages, ensuring that businesses can grow and compete on a global scale.

Venture Capital Investments in the Later Stage Venture Phase Between 2007 and 2022. The analysis of venture capital investments in the later stage venture phase between 2007 and 2022 reveals significant transformations in the global venture capital landscape with varying impacts depending on the country. While some countries have registered exponential increases, others have seen a reduction in investments, reflecting a series of economic, political, and market factors that influence the venture capital ecosystem. Israel shows the most extraordinary growth, with a 4636.86% increase in investments, rising from \$180 million in 2007 to \$8,526.35 million in 2022. This increase reflects the expansion and maturation of its technological ecosystem, which continues to attract large amounts of venture capital. Canada and Czechia have also recorded notable increases, with growths of 203.64% and 3126.62% respectively. Canada has benefited from an environment favorable to emerging technologies and robust government support, while Czechia has seen significant development in its technology sector, which has begun to gain international recognition. Other countries such as Estonia, Lithuania, and Spain have shown significant increases, highlighting how even smaller economies can emerge as important innovation centers thanks to favorable policies and targeted investments in key sectors. Countries like Finland, France, and Germany have seen moderate growth, which, while significant, reflects a more manageable pace of development within already mature and diversified economies. This suggests continuous consolidation rather than a sudden boom in venture capital activity. Conversely, Luxembourg, Norway, Portugal, and the United Kingdom have recorded declines in investments. In particular, Luxembourg and Portugal have seen considerable reductions, of -54.18% and -95.98% respectively. These declines can be attributed to various causes, including changes in tax policies, broader economic challenges, or a reduction in attractiveness as venture capital destinations. The United Kingdom showed a contraction of 14.74%, which could reflect political uncertainties such as the implications of Brexit on the venture capital market. Similarly, Norway saw a drastic reduction of 88.95%, possibly due to a shift in investment priorities or a decline in the availability of attractive investment opportunities. The United States continues to dominate the field with a 315.74% growth, further consolidating its role as a world leader in venture capital. This increase reflects the depth and breadth of the American market, as well as its constant capacity to innovate and attract capital. In conclusion, the analysis of the evolution of venture capital investments in the later stage phase between 2007 and 2022 shows a dynamic global landscape with significant variations among different countries. While some countries are emerging as new leaders in innovation, others face challenges that require a rethinking of strategies to attract venture capital.

Economic Policies to Increase Venture Capital Investments in the Later Stage Phase. In the context of OECD countries, boosting venture capital investments in the later stage venture phase is a strategic goal that can stimulate economic growth, promote innovation, and support job creation. To achieve these objectives it is essential that public policies aim to create a favorable environment that attracts and increases venture capital investments. This can be achieved through a combination of tax incentives, regulatory reforms, infrastructural support, and international collaboration initiatives. A key element in attracting later stage venture capital investments is the structuring of competitive tax incentives. Governments can introduce significant tax deductions for venture capital investors, such as reductions on capital gains taxes derived from investments in startups that reach maturity. Other

measures can include temporary tax exemptions for expanding startups and tax credits for research and development expenses to stimulate continuous innovation. The establishment of public-private co-investment funds can be another powerful tool to stimulate later stage investments. These funds, managed in collaboration between the public and private sectors, can offer capital on favorable terms, reducing financial risk for private investors and increasing the attractiveness of investments in mature companies. Notable examples include the European Investment Fund (EIF) program, which provides capital to venture capital and private equity funds that invest in European companies. To facilitate access to later stage venture capital, it is essential to simplify regulations and bureaucratic processes. This includes facilitating IPOs and mergers and acquisitions by reducing regulatory requirements and creating 'fast tracks' for regulatory approvals. Additionally, greater transparency and predictability in the regulatory process can increase investor confidence. Supporting the development of well-functioning capital markets is crucial to offering mature companies diverse options for raising funds. This includes strengthening stock exchanges and promoting alternative trading platforms that better serve the needs of SMEs. Creating market segments dedicated to mature startups can facilitate their visibility and access to institutional and private investors. Encouraging an international collaboration network through bilateral or multilateral agreements can help startups expand beyond national borders. This not only opens up new market opportunities but also access to new sources of capital. Initiatives like the European Union's Horizon Europe are examples of how support for international collaboration can be structured. Investing in education and training can ensure that a qualified workforce is available for growing startups. Specific programs can include entrepreneurial and technical training, as well as the promotion of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) in schools and universities. This ensures not only the growth of internal capabilities but also the attractiveness of the entrepreneurial environment. Finally, encouraging companies to incorporate sustainability and social responsibility goals can improve not only their image but also their market performance. Investors are increasingly oriented towards companies that demonstrate a commitment to environmental sustainability and social responsibility, and policies that support these goals can increase the attractiveness of later stage companies.

Conclusions. Venture capital investments in the later stage venture phase have grown on average by 301.44% in OECD countries between 2007 and 2022, increasing from \$1,127.91 million to \$4,527.87 million. Considering the concentration among countries, the United States ranks first with a value of 82.49%, followed by Israel with 7.53% and Canada with 2.92%. This results in a significant concentration in North America, particularly in the United States. Israel also achieves highly relevant results in funding later stage venture capital. Europe, on the other hand, remains far behind, showing a lag in institutions and financial organizations unable to find resources to support productive investments of new entrepreneurs in new technologies.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Later Stage Venture Capital Investments - 2022

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